

Fig. 3. Values of $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ for Pb^{2+} in *n*-butyl thioglycolate media at 27°.

(○) $F_2(X)$; (— — —) $F_3(X)$.

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A Study of Oxozirconium-1-nitroso-2-naphthol Complex and Colorimetric Estimation of Zirconium

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The potentialities of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol as a colorimetric reagent seem to be considerable in view of its colour reactions with many metals yet it has rarely been used as a colorimetric reagent. We report the results of our study of its use as a reagent for zirconium with which it is found to form a 1:1 complex.

The reagent, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (BDH), was recrystallised from methanol and water and a solution ($5.314 \times 10^{-4} M$) was obtained by dissolution of the solid in 50% ethanol-water. Oxozirconium chloride (Fluka) was recrystallised twice from conc. hydrochloric acid. The zirconium content was determined gravimetrically using oxine as a precipitant¹. A stock solution of the salt ($5.249 \times 10^{-4} M$) was used. Other chemicals were reagent grade. Twice distilled water was used for solutions. Measurement of

hydrogen ion concentrations was made with a Beckmann pH meter. Absorption measurements were made with a Hilger Spekker absorptiometer.

Absorptions were measured at 490 nm. The optical density was found to be a maximum in the pH range 2.5–3.5 and the pH of 3.5 was used for all measurements. Job's method² and the mole ratio method³ gave data (Table 1) which indicate a 1:1 complex. The molar extinction coefficient of the

TABLE 1. JOB'S METHOD AND MOLE RATIO METHOD

Zirconium(IV) solution ($5.249 \times 10^{-4} M$) (ml)	Reagent solution added ($5.314 \times 10^{-4} M$) (ml)	Absorbance of the complex (corrected readings)
Job's method		
1.0	9.0	0.034
2.0	8.0	0.059
3.0	7.0	0.064
4.0	6.0	0.087
4.5	5.5	0.094
5.0	5.0	0.106
6.0	4.0	0.098
7.0	3.0	0.090
8.0	2.0	0.070
9.0	1.0	0.040
Mole ratio method		
5.0	1.0	0.032
5.0	2.0	0.051
5.0	3.0	0.060
5.0	4.0	0.068
5.0	5.0	0.078
5.0	6.0	0.079
5.0	7.0	0.081
5.0	8.0	0.080

complex at this pH and 490 nm was 6.25×10^3 . Beer's law was obeyed in the range of 0–60 ppm of the metal ion. The method is not highly sensitive, the spectrophotometric sensitivity according to Sandell being $0.44 \mu g$ per cm^2 . The reagent is suitable for the analysis of micro quantities of zirconium where other methods fail or are not applicable. Interferences were studied by employing synthetic mixtures. Titanium(IV), aluminum, magnesium and calcium had no effect even when they were present in appreciable concentrations. Thorium(IV), uranium(VI), iron(III) and manganese(II) interfere as they also form soluble complexes under similar conditions. Anions like halides and nitrates do not interfere. Fluorides, phosphates and sulphates interfere seriously due to their complexing action on zirconium ions.

References

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